

Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 11

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Abstract

*During past years author worked with **borderedmagic squares** of even number blocks. These are based on equal sums magic squares of orders 4, 6, 8, 10, etc. This type of work is an extension of classical bordered magic squares. In case of multiples of 4, the extension is made for **pandiagonal** magic squares [23]. For multiples of order 6 refer Taneja [24]. Recently, author worked on multiples of 3, 5, 7 and 9. These are based on different sums of magic squares of order 3, 5, 7 and 9 [?, 29, 30, 31]. This work is for multiples of 11. This work is revised and enlarged version of previous work. We have worked with 20 different types of magic squares of order 11. Total work is up to order 154, but due to space problems the examples given here are only up to order 44. Higher order examples can be seen in **Excel files** attached with the work.*

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1 Introduction

During past years author [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8] worked with **block-wise** magic squares from orders 12 to 47. Author [9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14] also worked with **bordered** magic squares. The study on **bordered** magic squares is extended to **block-bordered** magic squares [15, 16, 17]. This is specially done for the magic squares of orders p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. This study is still extended to **block-wise bordered** magic squares [18, 19, 20, 21]. Some conection with Pythagorean triples and area-representations are also made [23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. The main property of **bordered** magic squares is that if we remove external borders, still we get **sub-bordered** magic squares, i.e., each layer in itself lead us to magic squares. In many cases, the properties of **bordered** magic square are seperated by **even** and **odd** orders magic squares. In many cases, we get good properties for the **even** order **bordered** magic squares. In some cases, we have to use fractional numbers to reach minimum perfect square sum of entries. For more study on **bordered** magic squares refer H. White’s web-site [1].

The idea of bordered magic squares is already discussed by H. White’s web-site [1] where the borders are of **single digits**. Borders multiples of even numbers starting from order 4 are done extensively by author [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28].

1.1 Summary of Bordered Magic Squares

1.1.1 Odd Numbers Multiples

- **Single Digit:** Bordered magic squares based on single digit [9, 10, 1].
- **Three Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 3 [?].
- **Five Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 5 [29].
- **Seven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 7 [30].
- **Nine Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 9 [31]
- **Eleven Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 11 [32] (This work)

1.1.2 Even Numbers Multiples

- **Two Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic rectangles multiples of 2 [72, 73, 61, 62, 62, 63].
- **Four Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 4 [23].
- **Six Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 6 [24].
- **Eight Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 8 [25].
- **Ten Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 10 [26].
- **Twelve Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 12 [27].
- **Fourteen Digits:** Bordered magic squares based on magic squares of order 14 [28].

The advantage in working with even number multiples is that we can work with equal sums blocks of magic squares.

It is revised version of author's previous work. In the previous work we worked only with three types of magic squares of order 11. Here are working with 20 types of magic square of order 11. The procedure, how these bordered magic squares are obtained is also given. Higher orders examples can be seen in **Excel file** attached with this work.

2 Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 11

Let's consider following three magic squares of order 11.

Let's consider following eleven of magic squares of order 9.

	pan	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	2	mgc	622	651	662	698	669	675	644	680	691	718	671
671	1	21	30	39	48	57	77	86	95	104	113	671	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671	
671	101	121	9	18	27	36	45	65	74	83	92	671	121	42	91	50	47	84	52	40	89	54	1	671	
671	80	89	109	118	6	15	24	44	53	62	71	671	119	55	41	87	48	43	92	53	45	85	3	671	
671	59	68	88	97	106	115	3	12	32	41	50	671	117	86	51	46	88	56	39	90	49	44	5	671	
671	38	47	56	76	85	94	103	112	11	20	29	671	115	60	28	95	65	21	97	58	26	99	7	671	
671	17	26	35	55	64	73	82	91	100	120	8	671	11	100	59	24	93	61	29	98	63	22	111	671	
671	117	5	14	23	43	52	61	70	79	99	108	671	13	23	96	64	25	101	57	27	94	62	109	671	
671	96	105	114	2	22	31	40	49	58	67	87	671	15	78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	107	671	
671	75	84	93	102	111	10	19	28	37	46	66	671	17	37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	105	671	
671	54	63	72	81	90	110	119	7	16	25	34	671	19	68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	103	671	
	33	42	51	60	69	78	98	107	116	4	13	671	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671	
1	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	
3	mgc	612	702	646	604	700	638	734	700	644	730	671	4	mgc	500	765	849	660	640	570	752	518	735	721	671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	17	105	671	
	121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	671	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	102	20	671	
	119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	671	22	100	37	43	80	67	78	72	50	28	94	671	
	117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	671	114	8	85	79	42	55	44	82	40	91	31	671	
	115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	671	15	107	73	49	60	59	64	46	76	98	24	671	
	11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	671	26	96	84	38	65	61	57	52	70	11	111	671	
	13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	671	87	35	56	66	58	63	62	53	69	97	25	671	
	15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	671	18	104	51	71	39	47	77	74	68	103	19	671	
	17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	671	116	6	41	81	83	75	45	48	54	2	120	671	
	19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	671	118	4	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671	
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671	33	89	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671	
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	

5	mgc	546	701	894	635	669	559	703	504	753	746	671	6	mgc	717	636	483	881	613	561	833	699	671	616	671
	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	17	105	671		33	86	22	90	30	85	81	46	76	109	13	671
	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	102	20	671		89	36	100	32	92	37	41	44	78	14	108	671
	22	100	60	65	58	56	66	78	44	28	94	671		29	93	52	49	67	69	68	80	42	114	8	671
	114	8	59	61	63	53	69	74	48	91	31	671		34	88	72	62	57	64	50	43	79	117	5	671
	15	107	64	57	62	72	50	38	84	98	24	671		91	31	56	63	61	59	66	95	27	16	106	671
	26	96	52	54	55	73	71	41	81	11	111	671		24	98	71	58	65	60	51	23	99	119	3	671
	87	35	70	68	67	51	49	76	46	97	25	671		83	39	54	73	55	53	70	96	26	17	105	671
	18	104	40	37	79	39	80	75	77	103	19	671		82	40	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	18	104	671
	116	6	82	85	43	83	42	45	47	2	120	671		84	38	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	15	107	671
	118	4	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671		7	111	103	6	1	4	113	2	110	112	102	671
	33	89	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671		115	11	19	116	121	118	9	120	12	20	10	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
	7	mgc	672	749	539	904	504	539	783	741	671	608		671	8	mgc	776	536	590	773	698	548	734	756	671
94		22	24	26	27	90	88	86	92	117	5	671	80	31		72	75	38	70	64	96	23	109	13	671
101		44	48	46	81	82	84	42	21	18	104	671	67	81		35	74	79	30	24	59	100	14	108	671
99		85	52	49	69	67	68	37	23	114	8	671	36	71		76	34	66	83	95	28	60	114	8	671
97		83	72	62	57	64	50	39	25	119	3	671	62	94		27	57	101	25	82	33	68	117	5	671
29		43	56	63	61	59	66	79	93	16	106	671	22	63		98	29	61	93	69	77	37	16	106	671
31		45	71	58	65	60	51	77	91	109	13	671	99	26		58	97	21	65	32	73	78	119	3	671
33		47	54	73	53	55	70	75	89	17	105	671	44	49		90	39	56	88	46	51	86	17	105	671
35		80	74	76	41	40	38	78	87	14	108	671	85	45		53	92	43	48	87	41	55	18	104	671
30		100	98	96	95	32	34	36	28	15	107	671	54	89		40	52	84	47	50	91	42	15	107	671
2		113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	112	102	671	4	111		103	6	1	7	113	2	110	112	102	671
120		9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	20	10	671	118	11		19	116	121	115	9	120	12	20	10	671
671		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

9	mgc	516	749	831	631	715	587	690	544	732	715	671
	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	17	105	671
	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	102	20	671
	22	100	85	77	69	61	53	45	37	28	94	671
	114	8	46	38	79	78	70	62	54	91	31	671
	15	107	63	55	47	39	80	72	71	98	24	671
	26	96	73	65	64	56	48	40	81	11	111	671
	87	35	41	82	74	66	58	57	49	97	25	671
	18	104	51	50	42	83	75	67	59	103	19	671
	116	6	68	60	52	44	43	84	76	2	120	671
	118	4	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
	33	89	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
10	mgc	532	739	800	659	644	599	701	521	762	753	671
	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	17	105	671
	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	102	20	671
	22	100	44	48	46	81	82	84	42	28	94	671
	114	8	85	52	49	69	67	68	37	91	31	671
	15	107	83	72	62	57	64	50	39	98	24	671
	26	96	43	56	63	61	59	66	79	11	111	671
	87	35	45	71	58	65	60	51	77	97	25	671
	18	104	47	54	73	53	55	70	75	103	19	671
	116	6	80	74	76	41	40	38	78	2	120	671
	118	4	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
	33	89	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
11	mgc	549	750	816	638	644	599	709	524	758	723	671
	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	17	105	671
	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	102	20	671
	22	100	44	48	46	81	82	84	42	28	94	671
	114	8	85	60	65	58	56	66	37	91	31	671
	15	107	83	59	61	63	53	69	39	98	24	671
	26	96	43	64	57	62	72	50	79	11	111	671
	87	35	45	52	54	55	73	71	77	97	25	671
	18	104	47	70	68	67	51	49	75	103	19	671
	116	6	80	74	76	41	40	38	78	2	120	671
	118	4	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
	33	89	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
12	mgc	550	718	894	635	682	558	695	515	753	710	671
	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	17	105	671
	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	102	20	671
	22	100	73	67	61	55	49	74	48	28	94	671
	114	8	56	50	69	68	62	78	44	91	31	671
	15	107	64	63	57	51	70	38	84	98	24	671
	26	96	52	71	65	59	58	41	81	11	111	671
	87	35	60	54	53	72	66	76	46	97	25	671
	18	104	40	37	79	39	80	75	77	103	19	671
	116	6	82	85	43	83	42	45	47	2	120	671
	118	4	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
	33	89	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

13	mgc	524	723	893	635	661	556	705	536	753	724	671	
		10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	17	105	671
		112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	102	20	671
		22	100	52	49	67	69	68	74	48	28	94	671
		114	8	72	62	57	64	50	78	44	91	31	671
		15	107	56	63	61	59	66	38	84	98	24	671
		26	96	71	58	65	60	51	41	81	11	111	671
		87	35	54	73	55	53	70	76	46	97	25	671
		18	104	39	37	79	40	80	75	77	103	19	671
		116	6	83	85	43	82	42	45	47	2	120	671
		118	4	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
		33	89	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
14	mgc	597	719	637	798	563	570	768	735	635	688	671	
		64	59	60	68	54	74	48	35	87	109	13	671
		57	61	65	67	55	78	44	98	24	18	104	671
		62	63	58	50	72	38	84	97	25	114	8	671
		66	70	69	49	51	41	81	33	89	119	3	671
		56	52	53	71	73	76	46	30	92	16	106	671
		39	37	79	40	80	75	77	93	29	117	5	671
		83	85	43	82	42	45	47	99	23	17	105	671
		101	26	31	95	34	32	100	36	94	14	108	671
		21	96	91	27	88	90	22	28	86	15	107	671
		2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	112	102	671
		120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	20	10	671
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
15	mgc	606	726	629	775	563	576	776	743	628	688	671	
		73	67	61	55	49	74	48	35	87	109	13	671
		56	50	69	68	62	78	44	98	24	18	104	671
		64	63	57	51	70	38	84	97	25	114	8	671
		52	71	65	59	58	41	81	33	89	119	3	671
		60	54	53	72	66	76	46	30	92	16	106	671
		39	37	79	40	80	75	77	93	29	117	5	671
		83	85	43	82	42	45	47	99	23	17	105	671
		101	26	31	95	34	32	100	36	94	14	108	671
		21	96	91	27	88	90	22	28	86	15	107	671
		2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	112	102	671
		120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	20	10	671
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
16	mgc	585	724	641	794	563	591	773	719	632	688	671	
		52	49	69	67	68	74	48	35	87	109	13	671
		72	62	57	64	50	78	44	98	24	18	104	671
		56	63	61	59	66	38	84	97	25	114	8	671
		71	58	65	60	51	41	81	33	89	119	3	671
		54	73	53	55	70	76	46	30	92	16	106	671
		39	37	79	40	80	75	77	93	29	117	5	671
		83	85	43	82	42	45	47	99	23	17	105	671
		101	26	31	95	34	32	100	36	94	14	108	671
		21	96	91	27	88	90	22	28	86	15	107	671
		2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	112	102	671
		120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	20	10	671
		671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

17	mgc	639	755	624	804	542	582	775	709	662	618	671
	85	77	69	61	53	45	37	35	87	109	13	671
	46	38	79	78	70	62	54	97	25	18	104	671
	63	55	47	39	80	72	71	98	24	114	8	671
	73	65	64	56	48	40	81	33	89	119	3	671
	41	82	74	66	58	57	49	30	92	16	106	671
	51	50	42	83	75	67	59	93	29	117	5	671
	68	60	52	44	43	84	76	99	23	17	105	671
	101	31	26	95	34	32	100	36	94	14	108	671
	21	91	96	27	88	90	22	28	86	15	107	671
2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	112	102	671	
120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	20	10	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
18	mgc	563	772	587	786	610	620	775	725	690	582	671
	44	48	46	81	82	84	42	35	87	109	13	671
	85	52	49	69	67	68	37	97	25	18	104	671
	45	72	62	57	64	50	77	93	29	114	8	671
	43	56	63	61	59	66	79	33	89	119	3	671
	83	71	58	65	60	51	39	30	92	16	106	671
	47	54	73	53	55	70	75	98	24	117	5	671
	80	74	76	41	40	38	78	99	23	17	105	671
	101	31	26	100	34	32	95	36	94	14	108	671
	21	91	96	22	88	90	27	28	86	15	107	671
2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	112	102	671	
120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	20	10	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
19	mgc	751	643	447	900	622	566	809	706	671	595	671
	33	86	22	90	30	85	81	46	76	109	13	671
	89	36	100	32	92	37	41	44	78	14	108	671
	29	93	64	68	51	70	52	96	26	114	8	671
	34	88	58	54	71	63	59	23	99	117	5	671
	91	31	56	66	61	50	72	95	27	16	106	671
	24	98	60	62	49	69	65	43	79	119	3	671
	83	39	67	55	73	53	57	80	42	17	105	671
	82	40	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	18	104	671
	84	38	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	15	107	671
4	111	103	6	1	7	113	2	110	112	102	671	
118	11	19	116	121	115	9	120	12	20	10	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671
20	mgc	735	622	483	871	629	568	831	675	671	625	671
	33	86	22	90	30	85	81	46	76	119	3	671
	89	36	100	32	92	37	41	44	78	14	108	671
	29	93	58	63	62	51	71	80	42	114	8	671
	34	88	65	61	57	49	73	43	79	117	5	671
	91	31	60	59	64	67	55	95	27	16	106	671
	24	98	69	68	52	66	50	23	99	109	13	671
	83	39	53	54	70	72	56	96	26	17	105	671
	82	40	47	77	25	94	35	101	48	18	104	671
	84	38	75	45	97	28	87	21	74	15	107	671
7	111	103	6	1	4	113	2	110	112	102	671	
115	11	19	116	121	118	9	120	12	20	10	671	
671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

2.1 Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 154 and 143

Let's consider **bordered** magic square of orders 13 and 14 given by

													1105
158	146	148	150	152	154	11	10	8	6	4	2	156	1105
23	136	126	128	130	132	33	32	30	28	26	134	147	1105
21	43	118	110	112	114	51	50	48	46	116	127	149	1105
19	41	59	104	98	100	65	64	62	102	111	129	151	1105
17	39	57	71	94	90	75	74	92	99	113	131	153	1105
15	37	55	69	79	88	81	86	91	101	115	133	155	1105
13	35	53	67	77	83	85	87	93	103	117	135	157	1105
161	139	121	107	97	84	89	82	73	63	49	31	9	1105
163	141	123	109	78	80	95	96	76	61	47	29	7	1105
165	143	125	68	72	70	105	106	108	66	45	27	5	1105
167	145	54	60	58	56	119	120	122	124	52	25	3	1105
169	36	44	42	40	38	137	138	140	142	144	34	1	1105
14	24	22	20	18	16	159	160	162	164	166	168	12	1105
1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105	1105

														1379
183	172	174	176	192	194	26	24	22	20	6	4	2	184	1379
19	159	150	152	167	169	48	46	44	31	29	27	160	178	1379
17	43	139	132	134	146	66	64	62	52	50	140	154	180	1379
15	40	61	123	118	129	80	78	69	67	124	136	157	182	1379
11	39	59	76	111	108	90	88	82	112	121	138	158	186	1379
9	34	55	75	87	106	103	94	91	110	122	142	163	188	1379
1	32	49	70	81	92	93	104	105	116	127	148	165	196	1379
179	155	137	120	113	95	98	99	102	84	77	60	42	18	1379
181	156	141	125	114	101	100	97	96	83	72	56	41	16	1379
185	161	143	126	85	89	107	109	115	86	71	54	36	12	1379
187	162	144	73	79	68	117	119	128	130	74	53	35	10	1379
189	164	57	65	63	51	131	133	135	145	147	58	33	8	1379
190	37	47	45	30	28	149	151	153	166	168	170	38	7	1379
13	25	23	21	5	3	171	173	175	177	191	193	195	14	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

The entries of above two magic squares are sequential numbers starting from 1:

$$D_{13 \times 13} := \{1, 2, \dots, 168, 169\}$$

$$D_{14 \times 14} := \{1, 2, \dots, 195, 196\}$$

The property of **bordered** magic squares is that removing the upper borders still we are left with magic squares of sequential values.

Multiplying each entry of above two magic squares of orders 13 and 14 by 121, we get

													133705
19118	17666	17908	18150	18392	18634	1331	1210	968	726	484	242	18876	133705
2783	16456	15246	15488	15730	15972	3993	3872	3630	3388	3146	16214	17787	133705
2541	5203	14278	13310	13552	13794	6171	6050	5808	5566	14036	15367	18029	133705
2299	4961	7139	12584	11858	12100	7865	7744	7502	12342	13431	15609	18271	133705
2057	4719	6897	8591	11374	10890	9075	8954	11132	11979	13673	15851	18513	133705
1815	4477	6655	8349	9559	10648	9801	10406	11011	12221	13915	16093	18755	133705
1573	4235	6413	8107	9317	10043	10285	10527	11253	12463	14157	16335	18997	133705
19481	16819	14641	12947	11737	10164	10769	9922	8833	7623	5929	3751	1089	133705
19723	17061	14883	13189	9438	9680	11495	11616	9196	7381	5687	3509	847	133705
19965	17303	15125	8228	8712	8470	12705	12826	13068	7986	5445	3267	605	133705
20207	17545	6534	7260	7018	6776	14399	14520	14762	15004	6292	3025	363	133705
20449	4356	5324	5082	4840	4598	16577	16698	16940	17182	17424	4114	121	133705
1694	2904	2662	2420	2178	1936	19239	19360	19602	19844	20086	20328	1452	133705
133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705	133705

$$121 \rightarrow 1, 2, \dots, 121$$

$$242 \rightarrow 122, 123, \dots, 242$$

$$363 \rightarrow 243, 244, \dots, 363$$

$$\dots \rightarrow \dots \dots$$

$$23595 \rightarrow 23475, 23476, \dots, 23595$$

$$23716 \rightarrow 23596, 23597 \dots, 23716$$

This lead us to two big **block-bordered** magic squares of orders 143 and 154. Since these two magic squares are very big, these are given in two **excel files** attached with this work. It is done with all the 20 magic squares of order 11. Thus we have 20 big magic squares of orders 143 and 154 multiples of 11.

The multiples blocks are 20 different kinds of magic squares of order 11. Based on these two big magic squares we get the following magic squares.

2.2 Magic Squares of Order 44

Below are three magic squares of order 44 obtained from magic squares of order 154. It is obtained by the application of the formula $\frac{a^2 - b^2}{2}$, $a > b$, i.e., subtract $\frac{154^2 - 44^2}{2} := 10890$ from each entry of magic square order 154, we get the following three magic squares of order 44:

1816	1836	1845	1854	1863	1872	1892	1901	1910	1919	1928	1453	1473	1482	1491	1500	1509	1529	1538	1547	1556	1565	364	384	393	402	411	420	440	449	458	467	476	1	21	30	39	48	57	77	86	95	104	113	42614
1916	1936	1824	1833	1842	1851	1860	1880	1889	1898	1907	1553	1573	1461	1470	1479	1488	1497	1517	1526	1535	1544	464	484	372	381	390	399	408	428	437	446	455	101	121	9	18	27	36	45	65	74	83	92	42614
1895	1904	1924	1933	1821	1830	1839	1859	1868	1877	1886	1532	1541	1561	1570	1458	1467	1476	1496	1505	1514	1523	443	452	472	481	369	378	387	407	416	425	434	80	89	109	118	6	15	24	44	53	62	71	42614
1874	1883	1903	1912	1921	1930	1818	1827	1847	1856	1865	1511	1520	1540	1549	1558	1567	1455	1464	1484	1493	1502	422	431	451	460	469	478	366	375	395	404	413	59	68	88	97	106	115	3	12	32	41	50	42614
1853	1862	1871	1891	1900	1909	1918	1927	1826	1835	1844	1490	1499	1508	1528	1537	1546	1555	1564	1463	1472	1481	401	410	419	439	448	457	466	475	374	383	392	38	47	56	76	85	94	103	112	11	20	29	42614
1832	1841	1850	1870	1879	1888	1897	1906	1915	1935	1823	1469	1478	1487	1507	1516	1525	1534	1543	1552	1572	1460	380	389	398	418	427	436	445	454	463	483	371	17	26	35	55	64	73	82	91	100	120	8	42614
1932	1820	1829	1838	1858	1867	1876	1885	1894	1914	1923	1569	1457	1466	1475	1495	1504	1513	1522	1531	1551	1560	480	368	377	386	406	415	424	433	442	462	471	117	5	14	23	43	52	61	70	79	99	108	42614
1911	1920	1929	1817	1837	1846	1855	1864	1873	1882	1902	1548	1557	1566	1454	1474	1483	1492	1501	1510	1519	1539	459	468	477	365	385	394	403	412	421	430	450	96	105	114	2	22	31	40	49	58	67	87	42614
1890	1899	1908	1917	1926	1825	1834	1843	1852	1861	1881	1527	1536	1545	1554	1563	1462	1471	1480	1489	1498	1518	438	447	456	465	474	373	382	391	400	409	429	75	84	93	102	111	10	19	28	37	46	66	42614
1869	1878	1887	1896	1905	1925	1934	1822	1831	1840	1849	1506	1515	1524	1533	1542	1562	1571	1459	1468	1477	1486	417	426	435	444	453	473	482	370	379	388	397	54	63	72	81	90	110	119	7	16	25	34	42614
1848	1857	1866	1875	1884	1893	1913	1922	1931	1819	1828	1485	1494	1503	1512	1521	1530	1550	1559	1568	1456	1465	396	405	414	423	432	441	461	470	479	367	376	33	42	51	60	69	78	98	107	116	4	13	42614
122	142	151	160	169	178	198	207	216	225	234	243	263	272	281	290	299	319	328	337	346	355	1574	1594	1603	1612	1621	1630	1650	1659	1668	1677	1686	1695	1715	1724	1733	1742	1751	1771	1780	1789	1798	1807	42614
222	242	130	139	148	157	166	186	195	204	213	343	363	251	260	269	278	287	307	316	325	334	1674	1694	1582	1591	1600	1609	1618	1638	1647	1656	1665	1795	1815	1703	1712	1721	1730	1739	1759	1768	1777	1786	42614
201	210	230	239	127	136	145	165	174	183	192	322	331	351	360	248	257	266	286	295	304	313	1653	1662	1682	1691	1579	1588	1597	1617	1626	1635	1644	1774	1783	1803	1812	1700	1709	1718	1738	1747	1756	1765	42614
180	189	209	218	227	236	124	133	153	162	171	301	310	330	339	348	357	245	254	274	283	292	1632	1641	1661	1670	1679	1688	1576	1585	1605	1614	1623	1753	1762	1782	1791	1800	1809	1697	1706	1726	1735	1744	42614
159	168	177	197	206	215	224	233	132	141	150	280	289	298	318	327	336	345	354	253	262	271	1611	1620	1629	1649	1658	1667	1676	1685	1584	1593	1602	1732	1741	1750	1770	1779	1788	1797	1806	1705	1714	1723	42614
138	147	156	176	185	194	203	212	221	241	129	259	268	277	297	306	315	324	333	342	362	250	1590	1599	1608	1628	1637	1646	1655	1664	1673	1693	1581	1711	1720	1729	1749	1758	1767	1776	1785	1794	1814	1702	42614
238	126	135	144	164	173	182	191	200	220	229	359	247	256	265	285	294	303	312	321	341	350	1690	1578	1587	1596	1616	1625	1634	1643	1652	1672	1681	1811	1699	1708	1717	1737	1746	1755	1764	1773	1793	1802	42614
217	226	235	123	143	152	161	170	179	188	208	338	347	356	244	264	273	282	291	300	309	329	1669	1678	1687	1575	1595	1604	1613	1622	1631	1640	1660	1790	1799	1808	1696	1716	1725	1734	1743	1752	1761	1781	42614
196	205	214	223	232	131	140	149	158	167	187	317	326	335	344	353	252	261	270	279	288	308	1648	1657	1666	1675	1684	1583	1592	1601	1610	1619	1639	1769	1778	1787	1796	1805	1704	1713	1722	1731	1740	1760	42614
175	184	193	202	211	231	240	128	137	146	155	296	305	314	323	332	352	361	249	258	267	276	1627	1636	1645	1654	1663	1683	1692	1580	1589	1598	1607	1748	1757	1766	1775	1784	1804	1813	1701	1710	1719	1728	42614
154	163	172	181	190	199	219	228	237	125	134	275	284	293	302	311	320	340	349	358	246	255	1606	1615	1624	1633	1642	1651	1671	1680	1689	1577	1586	1727	1736	1745	1754	1763	1772	1792	1801	1810	1698	1707	42614
485	505	514	523	532	541	561	570	579	588	597	848	868	877	886	895	904	924	933	942	951	960	969	989	998	1007	1016	1025	1045	1054	1063	1072	1081	1332	1352	1361	1370	1379	1388	1408	1417	1426	1435	1444	42614
585	605	493	502	511	520	529	549	558	567	576	948	968	856	865	874	883	892	912	921	930	939	1069	1089	977	986	995	1004	1013	1033	1042	1051	1060	1432	1452	1340	1349	1358	1367	1376	1396	1405	1414	1423	42614
564	573	593	602	490	499	508	528	537	546	555	927	936	956	965	853	862	871	891	900	909	918	1048	1057	1077	1086	974	983	992	1012	1021	1030	1039	1411	1420	1440	1449	1337	1346	1355	1375	1384	1393	1402	42614
543	552	572	581	590	599	487	496	516	525	534	906	915	935	944	953	962	850	859	879	888	897	1027	1036	1056	1065	1074	1083	971	980	1000	1009	1018	1390	1399	1419	1428	1437	1446	1334	1343	1363	1372	1381	42614
522	531	540	560	569	578	587	596	495	504	513	885	894	903	923	932	941	950	959	858	867	876	1006	1015	1024	1044	1053	1062	1071	1080	979	988	997	1369	1378	1387	1407	1416	1425	1434	1443	1342	1351	1360	42614
501	510	519	539	548	557	566	575	584	604	492	864	873	882	902	911	920	929	938	947	967	855	985	994	1003	1023	1032	1041	1050	1059	1068	1088	976	1348	1357	1366	1386	1395	1404	1413	1422	1431	1451	1339	42614
601	489	498	507	527	536	545	554	563	583	592	964	852	861	870	890	899	908	917	926	946	955	1085	973	982	991	1011	1020	1029	1038	1047	1067	1076	1448	1336	1345	1354	1374	1383	1392	1401	1410	1430	1439	42614
580	589	598	486	506	515	524	533	542	551	571	943	952	961	849	869	878	887	896	905	914	934	1064	1073	1082	970	990	999	1008	1017	1026	1035	1055	1427	1436	1445	1333	1353	1362	1371	1380	1389	1398	1418	42614
559	568	577	586	595	494	503	512	521	530	550	922	931	940	949	958	857	866	875	884	893	913	1043	1052	1061	1070	1079	978	987	996	1005	1014	1034	1406	1415	1424	1433	1442	1341	1350	1359	1368	1377	1397	42614
538	547	556	565	574	594	603	491	500	509	518	901	910	919	928	937	957	966	854	863	872	881	1022	1031	1040																				

1827	1835	1833	1831	1829	1828	1829	1931	1933	1935	1825	1464	1472	1470	1468	1466	1565	1566	1568	1570	1572	1462	375	383	381	379	377	476	477	479	481	483	373	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	42614
1936	1843	1915	1913	1911	1910	1847	1849	1851	1845	1816	1573	1480	1552	1550	1548	1547	1484	1486	1488	1482	1453	484	391	463	461	459	458	395	397	399	393	364	121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	42614
1934	1836	1893	1889	1891	1856	1855	1853	1895	1916	1818	1571	1473	1530	1526	1528	1493	1492	1490	1532	1553	1455	482	384	441	437	439	404	403	401	443	464	366	119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	42614
1932	1838	1852	1885	1888	1868	1870	1869	1900	1914	1820	1569	1475	1489	1522	1525	1505	1507	1506	1537	1551	1457	480	386	400	433	436	416	418	417	448	462	368	117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	42614
1930	1840	1854	1865	1875	1880	1873	1887	1898	1912	1822	1567	1477	1491	1502	1512	1517	1510	1524	1535	1549	1459	478	388	402	413	423	428	421	435	446	460	370	115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	42614
1826	1908	1894	1866	1874	1876	1878	1886	1858	1844	1926	1463	1545	1531	1503	1511	1513	1515	1523	1495	1481	1563	374	456	442	414	422	424	426	434	406	392	474	11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	42614
1828	1906	1892	1881	1879	1872	1877	1871	1860	1846	1924	1465	1543	1529	1518	1516	1509	1514	1508	1497	1483	1561	376	454	440	429	427	420	425	419	408	394	472	13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	42614
1830	1904	1890	1883	1864	1884	1882	1867	1862	1848	1922	1467	1541	1527	1520	1501	1521	1519	1504	1499	1485	1559	378	452	438	431	412	432	430	415	410	396	470	15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	42614
1832	1902	1857	1863	1861	1896	1897	1899	1859	1850	1920	1469	1539	1494	1500	1498	1533	1534	1536	1496	1487	1557	380	450	405	411	409	444	445	447	407	398	468	17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	42614
1834	1907	1837	1839	1841	1842	1905	1903	1901	1909	1918	1471	1544	1474	1476	1478	1479	1542	1540	1538	1546	1555	382	455	385	387	489	390	453	451	449	457	466	19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	42614
1927	1917	1919	1921	1923	1824	1823	1821	1819	1817	1925	1564	1554	1556	1558	1560	1461	1460	1458	1456	1454	1562	475	465	467	469	471	372	371	369	367	365	473	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	42614
133	141	139	137	135	234	235	237	239	241	131	254	262	260	258	256	355	356	358	360	362	252	1585	1593	1591	1589	1587	1686	1687	1689	1691	1693	1583	1706	1714	1712	1710	1708	1807	1808	1810	1812	1814	1704	42614
242	149	221	219	217	216	153	155	157	151	122	363	270	342	340	338	337	274	276	278	272	243	1694	1601	1673	1671	1669	1668	1605	1607	1609	1603	1574	1815	1722	1794	1792	1790	1789	1726	1728	1730	1724	1695	42614
240	142	199	195	197	162	161	159	201	222	124	361	263	320	316	318	283	282	280	322	343	245	1692	1594	1651	1647	1649	1614	1613	1611	1653	1674	1576	1813	1715	1772	1768	1770	1735	1734	1732	1774	1795	1697	42614
238	144	158	191	194	174	176	175	206	220	126	359	265	279	312	315	295	297	296	327	341	247	1690	1596	1610	1643	1646	1626	1628	1627	1658	1672	1578	1811	1717	1731	1764	1767	1747	1749	1748	1779	1793	1699	42614
236	146	160	171	181	186	179	193	204	218	128	357	267	281	292	302	307	300	314	325	339	249	1688	1598	1612	1623	1633	1638	1631	1645	1656	1670	1580	1809	1719	1733	1744	1754	1759	1752	1766	1777	1791	1701	42614
132	214	200	172	180	182	184	192	164	150	232	253	335	321	293	301	303	305	313	285	271	353	1584	1666	1652	1624	1632	1634	1636	1644	1616	1602	1684	1705	1787	1773	1745	1753	1755	1757	1765	1737	1723	1805	42614
134	212	198	187	185	178	183	177	166	152	230	255	333	319	308	306	299	304	298	287	273	351	1586	1664	1650	1639	1637	1630	1635	1629	1618	1604	1682	1707	1785	1771	1760	1758	1751	1756	1750	1739	1725	1803	42614
136	210	196	189	170	190	188	173	168	154	228	257	331	317	310	301	311	309	294	289	275	349	1588	1662	1648	1641	1622	1642	1640	1625	1620	1606	1680	1709	1783	1769	1762	1743	1763	1761	1746	1741	1727	1801	42614
138	208	163	169	167	202	203	205	165	156	226	259	329	284	290	288	323	324	326	286	277	347	1590	1660	1615	1621	1619	1654	1655	1657	1617	1608	1678	1711	1781	1736	1742	1740	1775	1776	1778	1738	1729	1799	42614
140	213	143	145	147	148	211	209	207	215	224	261	334	264	266	268	269	332	330	328	336	345	1592	1665	1595	1597	1599	1600	1663	1661	1659	1667	1676	1713	1786	1716	1718	1720	1721	1784	1782	1780	1788	1797	42614
233	223	225	227	229	130	129	127	125	123	231	354	344	346	348	350	251	250	248	246	244	352	1685	1675	1677	1679	1681	1582	1581	1579	1577	1575	1683	1806	1796	1798	1800	1802	1703	1702	1700	1698	1696	1804	42614
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598	492	543	545	547	537	553	558	532	575	515	961	855	906	908	910	900	916	921	895	938	878	1082	976	1027	1029	1031	1021	1037	1042	1016	1059	999	1445	1339	1390	1392	1394	1384	1400	1405	1379	1422	1362	42614	
499	591	548	541	546	556	534	522	568	582	508	862	954	911	904	909	919	897	885	931	945	871	983	1075	1032	1025	1030	1040	1018	1006	1052	1066	992	1346	1438	1395	1388	1393	1403	1381	1369	1415	1429	1355	42614	
510	580	536	538	539	557	555	525	565	495	595	873	943	899	901	902	920	918	888	928	858	958	994	1064	1020	1022	1023	1041	1039	1009	1049	979	1079	1357	1427	1383	1385	1386	1404	1402	1372	1412	1342	1442	42614	
571	519	554	552	551	535	533	560	530	581	509	934	882	917	915	914	898	896	923	893	944	872	1055	1003	1038	1036	1035	1019	1017	1044	1014	1065	993	1418	1366	1401	1399	1398	1382	1380	1407	1377	1428	1356	42614	
502	588	524	521	563	523	564	559	561	587	503	865	951	887	884	926	886	927	922	924	950	866	986	1072	1008	1005	1047	1007	1048	1043	1045	1071	987	1349	1435	1371	1368	1410	1370	1411	1406	1408	1434	1350	42614	
600	490	566	569	527	567	526	529	531																																					

15	mgc	44290	46706	48254	50774	51862	53850	56586	58390	59866	62042	63910	61714	60258	57934	56582	53798	51914	50778	48710	46314	44618	42614	40418	38962	36638	35286	32502	30618	29482	27414	25018	23322	21318	22994	25410	26958	29478	30566	32554	35290	37094	38570	40746	42614
1888	1882	1876	1870	1864	1889	1863	1850	1902	1924	1828	1525	1519	1513	1507	1501	1526	1500	1487	1539	1561	1465	436	430	424	418	412	437	411	398	450	472	376	73	67	61	55	49	74	48	35	87	109	13	42614	
1871	1865	1884	1883	1877	1893	1859	1913	1839	1833	1919	1508	1502	1521	1520	1514	1530	1496	1550	1476	1470	1556	419	413	432	431	425	441	407	461	387	381	467	56	50	69	68	62	78	44	98	24	18	104	42614	
1879	1878	1872	1866	1885	1853	1899	1912	1840	1929	1823	1516	1515	1509	1503	1522	1490	1536	1549	1477	1566	1460	427	426	420	414	433	401	447	460	388	477	371	64	63	57	51	70	38	84	97	25	114	8	42614	
1867	1886	1880	1874	1873	1856	1896	1848	1904	1934	1818	1504	1523	1517	1511	1510	1493	1533	1485	1541	1571	1455	415	434	428	422	421	404	444	396	452	482	366	52	71	65	59	58	41	81	33	89	119	3	42614	
1875	1869	1868	1887	1881	1891	1861	1845	1907	1831	1921	1512	1506	1505	1524	1518	1528	1498	1482	1544	1468	1558	423	417	416	435	429	439	409	393	455	379	469	60	54	53	72	66	76	46	30	92	16	106	42614	
1854	1852	1894	1855	1895	1890	1892	1908	1844	1932	1820	1491	1489	1531	1492	1532	1527	1529	1545	1481	1569	1457	402	400	442	403	443	438	440	456	392	480	368	39	37	79	40	80	75	77	93	29	117	5	42614	
1898	1900	1858	1897	1857	1860	1862	1914	1838	1832	1920	1535	1537	1495	1534	1494	1497	1499	1551	1475	1469	1557	446	448	406	445	405	408	410	462	386	380	468	83	85	43	82	42	45	47	99	23	17	105	42614	
1916	1841	1846	1910	1849	1847	1915	1851	1909	1829	1923	1553	1478	1483	1547	1486	1484	1552	1488	1546	1466	1560	464	389	394	458	397	395	463	399	457	377	471	101	26	31	95	34	32	100	36	94	14	108	42614	
1836	1911	1906	1842	1903	1905	1837	1843	1901	1830	1922	1473	1548	1543	1479	1540	1542	1474	1480	1538	1467	1559	384	459	454	390	451	453	385	391	449	378	470	21	96	91	27	88	90	22	28	86	15	107	42614	
1817	1928	1819	1821	1816	1926	1918	1822	1925	1927	1917	1454	1565	1456	1458	1453	1563	1555	1459	1562	1564	1554	365	476	367	369	364	474	466	391	470	473	475	465	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	112	102	42614
1935	1824	1933	1931	1936	1826	1834	1930	1827	1835	1825	1572	1461	1570	1568	1573	1463	1471	1567	1464	1472	1464	483	372	481	479	484	374	382	478	375	383	373	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	20	10	42614	
194	188	182	176	170	195	169	156	208	230	134	315	309	303	297	291	316	290	277	329	351	255	1646	1640	1634	1628	1622	1647	1621	1608	1660	1682	1586	1767	1761	1755	1749	1743	1768	1742	1729	1781	1803	1707	42614	
177	171	190	189	183	199	165	219	145	139	225	298	292	311	310	304	320	286	340	266	260	346	1629	1623	1642	1641	1635	1651	1617	1671	1597	1591	1677	1750	1744	1763	1762	1756	1772	1738	1792	1718	1712	1798	42614	
185	184	178	172	191	159	205	218	146	235	129	306	305	299	293	312	280	326	339	267	356	250	1637	1636	1630	1624	1643	1611	1657	1670	1598	1687	1581	1758	1757	1751	1745	1764	1732	1778	1791	1719	1808	1702	42614	
173	192	186	180	179	162	202	154	210	240	124	294	313	307	301	300	283	323	275	331	361	245	1625	1644	1638	1632	1631	1614	1654	1606	1662	1692	1576	1746	1765	1759	1753	1752	1735	1775	1727	1783	1813	1697	42614	
181	175	174	193	187	197	167	151	213	137	227	302	296	295	314	308	318	288	272	334	258	348	1633	1627	1626	1645	1639	1649	1619	1603	1665	1589	1679	1754	1748	1747	1766	1760	1770	1740	1724	1786	1710	1800	42614	
160	158	200	161	201	196	198	214	150	238	126	281	279	321	282	322	317	319	335	271	359	247	1612	1610	1652	1613	1653	1648	1650	1666	1602	1690	1578	1733	1731	1773	1734	1774	1769	1771	1787	1723	1811	1699	42614	
204	206	164	203	163	166	168	220	144	138	226	325	327	285	324	284	287	289	341	265	259	347	1656	1658	1616	1655	1615	1618	1620	1672	1596	1590	1678	1777	1779	1737	1776	1736	1739	1741	1793	1717	1711	1799	42614	
222	147	152	216	155	153	221	157	215	135	229	343	268	273	337	276	274	342	278	336	256	350	1674	1599	1604	1668	1607	1605	1673	1609	1667	1587	1681	1795	1720	1725	1789	1728	1726	1764	1730	1788	1708	1802	42614	
142	217	212	148	209	211	143	149	207	136	228	263	338	333	269	330	332	264	270	328	257	349	1594	1669	1664	1600	1661	1663	1595	1601	1659	1588	1680	1715	1790	1785	1721	1782	1784	1716	1722	1780	1709	1801	42614	
123	234	125	127	122	232	224	128	231	233	223	244	355	246	248	243	353	345	249	352	354	344	1575	1686	1577	1579	1574	1684	1676	1580	1683	1685	1675	1696	1807	1698	1700	1695	1805	1797	1701	1804	1806	1796	42614	
241	130	239	237	242	132	140	236	133	141	131	362	251	360	358	363	253	261	357	254	262	252	1693	1582	1691	1689	1694	1584	1592	1688	1585	1593	1583	1814	1703	1812	1810	1815	1705	1713	1809	1706	1714	1704	42614	
557	551	545	539	533	558	532	519	571	593	497	920	914	908	902	896	921	895	882	934	956	860	1041	1035	1029	1023	1017	1042	1016	1003	1055	1077	981	1404	1398	1392	1386	1380	1405	1379	1366	1418	1440	1344	42614	
540	534	553	552	546	562	528	582	508	502	588	903	897	916	915	909	925	891	945	871	865	951	1024	1018	1037	1036	1030	1046	1012	1066	992	986	1072	1387	1381	1400	1399	1393	1409	1375	1429	1355	1349	1435	42614	
548	547	541	535	554	522	568	581	509	598	492	911	910	904	898	917	885	931	944	872	961	855	1032	1031	1025	1019	1038	1006	1052	1065	993	1082	976	1395	1394	1388	1382	1401	1369	1415	1428	1356	1445	1339	42614	
536	555	549	543	542	525	565	517	573	603	487	899	918	912	906	905	888	928	880	936	966	850	1020	1039	1033	1027	1026	1009	1049	1001	1057	1087	971	1383	1402	1396	1390	1389	1372	1412	1364	1420	1450	1334	42614	
544	538	537	556	550	560	530	514	576	500	590	907	901	900	919	913	923	893	877	939	863	953	1028	1022	1021	1040	1034	1044	1014	998	1060	984	1074	1391	1385	1384	1403	1397	1407	1377	1361	1423	1347	1437	42614	
523	521	563	524	564	559	561	577	513	601	489	886	884	926	887	927	922	924	940	876	964	852	1007	1005	1047	1008	1048	1043	1045	1061	997	1085	973	1370	1368	1410	1371	1411	1406	1408	1424	1360	1448	1336	42614	
567	569	527	566	526	529	531	583	507	501	589	930	932	890	929	889	892	894	946	870	864	952	1051	1053	1011	1050	1010	1013	1015	1067	991	985	1073	1414	1416	1374	1413	1373	1376	1378	1430	1354	1348	1436	42614	
585	510	515	579	518	516	584	520	578	498	592	948	873	878	942	881	879	947	883	941	861	955	1069	994	999	1063	1002	1000	1068	1004	1062	982	1076	1432	1357	1362	1426	1365	1363	1431	1367	1425				

2.3 Magic Squares of Order 33

Below are three magic squares of order 33 obtained from magic squares of order 143. It is obtained by the application of the formula $\frac{a^2 - b^2}{2}$, $a > b$, i.e., subtract $\frac{143^2 - 33^2}{2} := 9680$ from each entry of magic square order 143, we get the following three magic squares of order 33:

																									17985									
859	867	865	863	861	960	961	963	965	967	857	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	617	625	623	621	619	718	719	721	723	725	615	17985	
968	889	938	897	894	931	899	887	936	901	848	121	42	91	50	47	84	52	40	89	54	1	726	647	696	655	652	689	657	645	694	659	606	17985	
966	902	888	934	895	890	939	900	892	932	850	119	55	41	87	48	43	92	53	45	85	3	724	660	646	692	653	648	697	658	650	690	608	17985	
964	933	898	893	935	903	886	937	896	891	852	117	86	51	46	88	56	39	90	49	44	5	722	691	656	651	693	661	644	695	654	649	610	17985	
962	907	875	942	912	868	944	905	873	946	854	115	60	28	95	65	21	97	58	26	99	7	720	665	633	700	670	626	702	663	631	704	612	17985	
858	947	906	871	940	908	876	945	910	869	958	11	100	59	24	93	61	29	98	63	22	111	616	705	664	629	698	666	634	703	668	627	716	17985	
860	870	943	911	872	948	904	874	941	909	956	13	23	96	64	25	101	57	27	94	62	109	618	628	701	669	630	706	662	632	699	667	714	17985	
862	925	920	879	930	913	881	923	918	883	954	15	78	73	32	83	66	34	76	71	36	107	620	683	678	637	688	671	639	681	676	641	712	17985	
864	884	924	916	877	926	921	882	928	914	952	17	37	77	69	30	79	74	35	81	67	105	622	642	682	674	635	684	679	640	686	672	710	17985	
866	915	880	929	917	885	922	919	878	927	950	19	68	33	82	70	38	75	72	31	80	103	624	673	638	687	675	643	680	677	636	685	708	17985	
959	949	951	953	955	856	855	853	851	849	957	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	717	707	709	711	713	614	613	611	609	607	715	17985	
254	262	260	258	256	355	356	358	360	362	252	496	504	502	500	498	597	598	600	602	604	494	738	746	744	742	740	839	840	842	844	846	736	17985	
363	284	333	292	289	326	294	282	331	296	243	605	526	575	534	531	568	536	524	573	538	485	847	768	817	776	773	810	778	766	815	780	727	17985	
361	297	283	329	290	285	334	295	287	327	245	603	539	525	571	532	527	576	537	529	569	487	845	781	767	813	774	769	818	779	771	811	729	17985	
359	328	293	288	330	298	281	332	291	286	247	601	570	535	530	572	540	523	574	533	528	489	843	812	777	772	814	782	765	816	775	770	731	17985	
357	302	270	337	307	263	339	300	268	341	249	599	544	512	579	549	505	581	542	510	583	491	841	786	754	821	791	747	823	784	752	825	733	17985	
253	342	301	266	335	303	271	340	305	264	353	495	584	543	508	577	545	513	582	547	506	595	737	826	785	750	819	787	755	824	789	748	837	17985	
255	265	338	306	267	343	299	269	336	304	351	497	507	580	548	509	585	541	511	578	546	593	739	749	822	790	751	827	783	753	820	788	835	17985	
257	320	315	274	325	308	276	318	313	278	349	499	562	557	516	567	550	518	560	555	520	591	741	804	799	758	809	792	760	802	797	762	833	17985	
259	279	319	311	272	321	316	277	323	309	347	501	521	561	553	514	563	558	519	565	551	589	743	763	803	795	756	805	800	761	807	793	831	17985	
261	310	275	324	312	280	317	314	273	322	345	503	552	517	566	554	522	559	556	515	564	587	745	794	759	808	796	764	801	798	757	806	829	17985	
354	344	346	348	350	251	250	248	246	244	352	596	586	588	590	592	493	492	490	488	486	594	838	828	830	832	834	735	734	732	730	728	836	17985	
375	383	381	379	377	476	477	479	481	483	373	980	988	986	984	982	1081	1082	1084	1086	1088	978	133	141	139	137	135	234	235	237	239	241	131	17985	
484	405	454	413	410	447	415	403	452	417	364	1089	1010	1059	1018	1015	1052	1020	1008	1057	1022	969	242	163	212	171	168	205	173	161	210	175	122	17985	
482	418	404	450	411	406	455	416	408	448	366	1087	1023	1009	1055	1016	1011	1060	1021	1013	1053	971	240	176	162	208	169	164	213	174	166	206	124	17985	
480	449	414	409	451	419	402	453	412	407	368	1085	1054	1019	1014	1056	1024	1007	1058	1017	1012	973	238	207	172	167	209	177	160	211	170	165	126	17985	
478	423	391	458	428	384	460	421	389	462	370	1083	1028	996	1063	1033	989	1065	1026	994	1067	975	236	181	149	216	186	142	218	179	147	220	128	17985	
374	463	422	387	456	424	392	461	426	385	474	979	1068	1027	992	1061	1029	997	1066	1031	990	1079	132	221	180	145	214	182	150	219	184	143	232	17985	
376	386	459	427	388	464	420	390	457	425	472	981	991	1064	1032	993	1069	1025	995	1062	1030	1077	134	144	217	185	146	222	178	148	215	183	230	17985	
378	441	436	395	446	429	397	439	434	399	470	983	1046	1041	1000	1051	1034	1002	1044	1039	1004	1075	136	199	194	153	204	187	155	197	192	157	228	17985	
380	400	440	432	393	442	437	398	444	430	468	985	1005	1045	1037	998	1047	1042	1003	1049	1035	1073	138	158	198	190	151	200	195	156	202	188	226	17985	
382	431	396	445	433	401	438	435	394	443	466	987	1036	1001	1050	1038	1006	1043	1040	999	1048	1071	140	189	154	203	191	159	196	193	152	201	224	17985	
475	465	467	469	471	372	371	369	367	365	473	1080	1070	1072	1074	1076	977	976	974	972	970	1078	233	223	225	227	229	130	129	127	125	123	231	17985	
17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985

7	mgc	19077	20397	20856	23040	22929	24123	25944	26907	27786	28686	29964	27789	25842	23034	21951	18573	16500	15054	12750	10362	7995	6006	7098	8418	8877	11061	10950	12144	13965	14928	15807	16707	17985	
941	869	871	873	874	937	935	933	939	964	852	94	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	92	117	5	699	627	629	631	632	695	693	691	697	722	610	17985		
948	891	895	893	928	929	931	889	868	865	951	101	44	48	46	81	82	84	42	21	18	104	706	649	653	651	686	687	689	647	626	623	709	17985		
946	932	899	896	916	914	915	884	870	961	855	99	85	52	49	69	67	68	37	23	114	8	704	690	657	654	674	672	673	642	628	719	613	17985		
944	930	919	909	904	911	897	886	872	966	850	97	83	72	62	57	64	50	39	25	119	3	702	688	677	667	662	669	655	644	630	724	608	17985		
876	890	903	910	908	906	913	926	940	863	953	29	43	56	63	61	59	66	79	93	16	106	634	648	661	668	666	664	671	684	698	621	711	17985		
878	892	918	905	912	907	898	924	938	956	860	31	45	71	58	65	60	51	77	91	109	13	636	650	676	663	670	665	656	682	696	714	618	17985		
880	894	901	920	900	902	917	922	936	864	952	33	47	54	73	53	55	70	75	89	17	105	638	652	659	678	658	660	675	680	694	622	710	17985		
882	927	921	923	888	887	885	925	934	861	955	35	80	74	76	41	40	38	78	87	14	108	640	685	679	681	646	645	643	683	692	619	713	17985		
877	947	945	943	942	879	881	883	875	862	954	30	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	28	15	107	635	705	703	701	700	637	639	641	633	620	712	17985		
849	960	851	853	848	958	950	854	957	959	949	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	112	102	607	718	609	611	606	716	708	612	715	717	707	17985		
967	856	965	963	968	858	866	962	859	867	857	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	20	10	725	614	723	721	726	616	624	720	617	625	615	17985		
336	264	266	268	269	332	330	328	334	359	247	578	506	508	510	511	574	572	570	576	601	489	820	748	750	752	753	816	814	812	818	843	731	17985		
343	286	290	288	323	324	326	284	263	260	346	585	528	532	530	565	566	568	526	505	502	588	827	770	774	772	807	808	810	768	747	744	830	17985		
341	327	294	291	311	309	310	279	265	356	250	583	569	536	533	553	551	552	521	507	598	492	825	811	778	775	795	793	794	763	749	840	734	17985		
339	325	314	304	299	306	292	281	267	361	245	581	567	556	546	541	548	534	523	509	603	487	823	809	798	788	783	790	776	765	751	845	729	17985		
271	285	298	305	303	301	308	321	335	258	348	513	527	540	547	545	543	550	563	577	500	590	755	769	782	789	787	785	792	805	819	742	832	17985		
273	287	313	300	307	302	293	319	333	351	255	515	529	555	542	549	544	535	561	575	593	497	757	771	797	784	791	786	777	803	817	835	739	17985		
275	289	296	315	295	297	312	317	331	259	347	517	531	538	557	537	539	554	559	573	501	589	759	773	780	799	779	781	796	801	815	743	831	17985		
277	322	316	318	283	282	280	320	329	256	350	519	564	558	560	525	524	522	562	571	498	592	761	806	800	802	767	766	764	804	813	740	834	17985		
272	342	340	338	337	274	276	278	270	257	349	514	584	582	580	579	516	518	520	512	499	591	756	826	824	822	821	758	760	762	754	741	833	17985		
244	355	246	248	243	353	345	249	352	354	344	486	597	488	490	485	595	587	491	594	596	586	728	839	730	732	727	837	829	733	836	838	828	17985		
362	251	360	358	363	253	261	357	254	262	252	604	493	602	600	605	495	503	599	496	504	494	846	735	844	842	847	737	745	841	738	746	736	17985		
457	385	387	389	390	453	451	449	455	480	368	1062	990	992	994	995	1058	1056	1054	1060	1085	973	215	143	145	147	148	211	209	207	213	238	126	17985		
464	407	411	409	444	445	447	405	384	381	467	1069	1012	1016	1014	1049	1050	1052	1010	989	986	1072	222	165	169	167	202	203	205	163	142	139	225	17985		
462	448	415	412	432	430	431	400	386	477	371	1067	1053	1020	1017	1037	1035	1036	1005	991	1082	976	220	206	173	170	190	188	189	158	144	235	129	17985		
460	446	435	425	420	427	413	402	388	482	366	1065	1051	1040	1030	1025	1032	1018	1007	993	1087	971	218	204	193	183	178	185	171	160	146	240	124	17985		
392	406	419	426	424	422	429	442	456	379	469	997	1011	1024	1031	1029	1027	1034	1047	1061	984	1074	150	164	177	184	182	180	187	200	214	137	227	17985		
394	408	434	421	428	423	414	440	454	472	376	999	1013	1039	1026	1033	1028	1019	1045	1059	1077	981	152	166	192	179	186	181	172	198	212	230	134	17985		
396	410	417	436	416	418	433	438	452	380	468	1001	1015	1022	1041	1021	1023	1038	1043	1057	985	1073	154	168	175	194	174	176	191	196	210	138	226	17985		
398	443	437	439	404	403	401	441	450	377	471	1003	1048	1042	1044	1009	1008	1006	1046	1055	982	1076	156	201	195	197	162	161	159	199	208	135	229	17985		
393	463	461	459	458	395	397	399	391	378	470	998	1068	1066	1064	1063	1000	1002	1004	996	983	1075	151	221	219	217	216	153	155	157	149	136	228	17985		
365	476	367	369	364	474	466	370	473	475	465	970	1081	972	974	969	1079	1071	975	1078	1080	1070	123	234	125	127	122	232	224	128	231	233	223	17985		
483	372	481	479	484	374	382	478	375	383	373	1088	977	1086	1084	1089	979	987	1083	980	988	978	241	130	239	237	242	132	140	236	133	141	131	17985		
17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985

10	mgc	17205	17463	17283	16497	16089	15591	15534	14631	14991	14601	13992	14301	15648	16557	16860	17541	18132	19164	19350	20799	21498	21978	21198	21456	21276	20490	20082	19584	19527	18624	18984	18594	17985		
373	393	476	464	471	456	451	364	368	380	468	978	998	1081	1069	1076	1061	1056	969	973	985	1073	131	151	234	222	229	214	209	122	126	138	226	17985			
475	455	372	384	377	392	397	484	480	465	383	1080	1060	977	989	982	997	1002	1089	1085	1070	988	233	213	130	142	135	150	155	242	238	223	141	17985			
385	463	407	411	409	444	445	447	405	391	457	990	1068	1012	1016	1014	1049	1050	1052	1010	996	1062	143	221	165	169	167	202	203	205	163	149	215	17985			
477	371	448	415	412	432	430	431	400	454	394	1082	976	1053	1020	1017	1037	1035	1036	1005	1059	999	235	129	206	173	170	190	188	189	158	212	152	17985			
378	470	446	435	425	420	427	413	402	461	387	983	1075	1051	1040	1030	1025	1032	1018	1007	1066	992	136	228	204	193	183	178	185	171	160	219	145	17985			
389	459	406	419	426	424	422	429	442	374	474	994	1064	1011	1024	1031	1029	1027	1034	1047	979	1079	147	217	164	177	184	182	180	187	200	132	232	17985			
450	398	408	434	421	428	423	414	440	460	388	1055	1003	1013	1039	1026	1033	1028	1019	1045	1065	993	208	156	166	192	179	186	181	172	198	218	146	17985			
381	467	410	417	436	416	418	433	438	466	382	986	1072	1015	1022	1041	1021	1023	1038	1043	1071	987	139	225	168	175	194	174	176	191	196	224	140	17985			
479	369	443	437	439	404	403	401	441	365	483	1084	974	1048	1042	1044	1009	1008	1006	1046	970	1088	237	127	201	195	197	162	161	159	199	123	241	17985			
481	367	390	386	482	473	478	376	453	399	379	1086	972	995	991	1087	1078	1083	981	1058	1004	984	239	125	148	144	240	231	236	134	211	157	137	17985			
396	452	458	462	366	375	370	472	395	449	469	1001	1057	1063	1067	971	980	975	1077	1000	1054	1074	154	210	216	220	124	133	128	230	153	207	227	17985			
252	272	355	343	350	335	330	243	247	259	347	494	514	597	585	592	577	572	485	489	501	589	736	756	839	827	834	819	814	727	731	743	831	17985			
354	334	251	263	256	271	276	363	359	344	262	596	576	493	505	498	513	518	605	601	586	504	838	818	735	747	740	755	760	847	843	828	746	17985			
264	342	286	290	288	323	324	326	284	270	336	506	584	528	532	530	565	566	568	526	512	578	748	826	770	774	772	807	808	810	768	754	820	17985			
356	250	327	294	291	311	309	310	279	333	273	598	492	569	536	533	553	551	552	521	575	515	840	734	811	778	775	795	793	794	763	817	757	17985			
257	349	325	314	304	299	306	292	281	340	266	499	591	567	556	546	541	548	534	523	582	508	741	833	809	798	788	783	790	776	765	824	750	17985			
268	338	285	298	305	303	301	308	321	253	353	510	580	527	540	547	545	543	550	563	495	595	752	822	769	782	789	787	785	792	805	737	837	17985			
329	277	287	313	300	307	302	293	319	339	267	571	519	529	555	542	549	544	535	561	581	509	813	761	771	797	784	791	786	777	803	823	751	17985			
260	346	289	296	315	295	297	312	317	345	261	502	588	531	538	557	537	539	554	559	587	503	744	830	773	780	799	779	781	796	801	829	745	17985			
358	248	322	316	318	283	282	280	320	244	362	600	490	564	558	560	525	524	522	562	486	604	842	732	806	800	802	767	766	764	804	728	846	17985			
360	246	269	265	361	352	357	255	332	278	258	602	488	511	507	603	594	599	497	574	520	500	844	730	753	749	845	836	841	739	816	762	742	17985			
275	331	337	341	245	254	249	351	274	328	348	517	573	579	583	487	496	491	593	516	570	590	759	815	821	825	729	738	733	835	758	812	832	17985			
857	877	960	948	955	940	935	848	852	864	952	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	17	105	615	635	718	706	713	698	693	606	610	622	710	17985			
959	939	856	868	861	876	881	968	964	949	867	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	102	20	717	697	614	626	619	634	639	726	722	707	625	17985			
869	947	891	895	893	928	929	931	889	875	941	22	100	44	48	46	81	82	84	42	28	94	627	705	649	653	651	686	687	689	647	633	699	17985			
961	855	932	899	896	916	914	915	884	938	878	114	8	85	52	49	69	67	68	37	91	31	719	613	690	657	654	674	672	673	642	696	636	17985			
862	954	930	919	909	904	911	897	886	945	871	15	107	83	72	62	57	64	50	39	98	24	620	712	688	677	667	662	669	655	644	703	629	17985			
873	943	890	903	910	908	906	913	926	858	958	26	96	43	56	63	61	59	66	79	11	111	631	701	648	661	668	666	664	671	684	616	716	17985			
934	882	892	918	905	912	907	898	924	944	872	87	35	45	71	58	65	60	51	77	97	25	692	640	650	676	663	670	665	656	682	702	630	17985			
865	951	894	901	920	900	902	917	922	950	866	18	104	47	54	73	53	55	70	75	103	19	623	709	652	659	678	658	660	675	680	708	624	17985			
963	853	927	921	923	888	887	885	925	849	967	116	6	80	74	76	41	40	38	78	2	120	721	611	685	679	681	646	645	643	683	607	725	17985			
965	851	874	870	966	957	962	860	937	883	863	118	4	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	723	609	632	628	724	715	720	618	695	641	621	17985			
880	936	942	946	850	859	854	956	879	933	953	33	89	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	638	694	700	704	608	617	612	714	637	691	711	17985			
17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985	17985

Above there are only five examples of magic squares of order 33 multiples of 11. The other examples are given in an **excel file** attached with the work.

3 Author's Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

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